

the brown planthopper and moderate resistance to green leafhopper and yellow stem borer. It is resistant to gall midge in several states of India.

In field tests, IR42 outyielded most IRRI varieties and elite lines on nutrient-deficient or toxic wetland rice soils and responded well to moderate

applications of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers.

Because it combines high yield potential with pest resistance and tolerance for nutrient deficiencies and soil toxicities (see table), IR42 may be a solution to the small rice farmer's problems. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Miniature deepwater tanks for screening chemicals against ufra

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Miniature deepwater tanks can be made from plastic soil pipe, 10 cm (4 inches) in diameter, cut into 1-m lengths. The pipes are sealed at the bottom with polythene and mounted upright in large earthenware pots of soil (see figure). Such tanks were used to determine the dosage of carbofuran needed to control ufra disease of deepwater rice, caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*,

after the appearance of symptoms in the vegetative phase.

Diseased tillers (those that exhibited early symptoms of attack, a faint chlorotic splash pattern on the young leaves) were transplanted from a field badly affected by ufra during August directly into the tubes at 3 tillers/tube. Furadan 3G was added to each tube at 1 of 5 rates (0, 1, 4, 7, 10 g), with 5 replications/rate, and the tubes were arranged in a 5 x 5 latin square. The water depth in each was maintained at 0.5 m. When the tubes were scored about 2 months later, symptoms were observed on 40% of the tillers in the control tubes, 35% in the tubes receiving 1 g of Furadan 3G, and none in the

other tubes. The chemotherapeutic effect of carbofuran is between 1 and 4 g of 3G granules/tube.

This simple technique may be adapted to screen many types of chemicals (applied as granule or foliar spray) for activity against ufra when the symptoms appear. It is superior to the use of inoculated tillers because the relationship between the nematode and its host develops under natural conditions until transplanting. It is also superior to field experimentation because reinfestation is completely excluded, the plot size can be reduced, and the number of replications can be increased correspondingly. ■

The ufra nematode population in deepwater rice in Bangladesh

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Ufra disease caused by the rice stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* devastates deepwater rice in southern Bangladesh. Infested crop residues cause primary infestation and water-borne inocula, secondary infestation during the growing season. Distinction between the two kinds of infestations is necessary when investigating the effect of treatments during land preparation. An examination of the nematode population in individual tillers during the vegetative phase can help in making such distinctions.

To determine the relative frequency of nematodes per individual tillers, a random sample of 50 tillers was taken from a field badly affected by ufra in Comilla district. Each tiller was cut off just below the top node, then truncated 15 cm above the node. Each segment was cut into 0.5-cm pieces and placed in a 7-ml bijou bottle with 2 ml water. After 24 hours the nematodes extracted by the water were counted with a Peters' 1-ml counting slide.

Three distinct modes in frequency distribution were found; the high mode was not continuous with the remainder

Miniature deepwater tanks for screening against ufra disease. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute.